

Appendices to: Newborn Be star systems observed shortly after mass transfer

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ABSTRACT

Context. Many classical Be stars acquire their very rapid rotation by mass and angular-momentum transfer in massive binaries, marking the first phase of the evolutionary chain. Later-stage products, such as Be+subdwarf and Be+neutron-star binaries (Be X-ray binaries), are also well known, although the search and definite proof for Be+white dwarf companions is ongoing. Short-lived intermediate-phase objects, i.e., binaries past the interaction stage but with the donor stars not yet having reached the end of their evolution/contraction, have only been discovered recently.

Aims. The main hallmark of the first such binaries of this kind is a system of absorption lines with low width, significant radial-velocity variations, and peculiar relative line strengths. Data archives and the literature can be searched for additional candidates exhibiting this pattern, and follow-up observations be obtained in order to increase the number of these systems with quantitatively known orbits to provide a basis for an initial statistical investigation and to develop observational strategies for abundance analyses.

Methods. Thirteen candidates were identified at various confidence levels. To verify the candidates' nature, orbital elements were derived from new high-quality spectra and interferometric observations where possible, qualitative analyses of other basic parameters were performed, and indicators of advanced stages of nucleosynthesis were preliminarily evaluated.

Results. Adding to the two known systems identified as classical Be star+pre-subdwarf binaries (LB-1 and HR 6819), two more (V742 Cas, HD 44637) could be confirmed with interferometry, with V742 Cas setting a new record for the smallest visually observed angular semi-major axis, at $a = 0.663$ mas. Two further ones (V447 Sct, V1362 Cyg) are not resolved interferometrically, but other evidence puts them at the same confidence level as LB-1. V2174 Cyg is a candidate with very high confidence, but was not observed interferometrically. The remaining ones are either candidates with varying levels of confidence, mainly so due to the lack of available spectroscopic or interferometric observations for comparison with the others and orbit determination, or could be rejected as candidates with the followup observations.

Conclusions. Of a mostly magnitude complete sample of 328 Be stars, 0.5–1% are found to have recently completed the mass overflow that led to their formation. Another 5% are systems with compact subdwarf companions, i.e., further evolved after a previous overflow, and possibly two more percent harbor white dwarfs. All these systems are of early B-subtypes, however, and if the original sample is restricted to early subtypes (136 objects), these percentages increase by a factor of about 2.5, while dropping to zero for the mid and late subtypes (together 204 objects). This strongly suggests that early- vs. mid- and late-type Be stars have differently weighted channels to acquire their rapid rotation, namely binary interaction vs. evolutionary spin-up.

Key words. Stars: massive – stars: emission-line, Be – circumstellar matter – binaries: spectroscopic – stars: individual: HR 6819, ALS 8775, V742 Cas, HD 44637, V447 Sct, V1362 Cyg, V2174 Cyg

Appendix A: Spectroscopic data

In this section, the measured radial velocities (RVs) used for the orbital solutions are listed, and some spectra are shown with a wider wavelength coverage than in the main body of the work. For an introduction to the instruments see Sect. 2. RV measurements were made by fitting a single Gaussian absorption profile to the line core. Due to the different resolutions and partly very narrow lines, some stars, like HR 2309 for He I $\lambda 6678$, reveal their blended nature only in the higher-resolution data. In that case, the Gaussian was fitted such that it covered all substructure, as if the line were unresolved. Since measurement errors are difficult to estimate for such a varied set of instruments, and from the data alone, generic values were adopted. For the combined dynamic solutions, individual weights were reduced by a factor of four for BeSS H α and a factor of two for BeSS echelle spectra.

Table A.1. Radial velocity measurements of the Si III $\lambda 4553$ line of V447 Sct.

Date MJD	Radial velocity [km s ⁻¹]	Source
58000.1197	-33.4	ARCES
58022.0989	35.9	ARCES
58028.0666	81.3	ARCES
58050.0492	32.5	ARCES
58301.2970	-65.6	ARCES
58375.1115	68.1	ARCES
58384.1210	107.7	ARCES
58397.0684	70.8	ARCES
58673.2039	105.7	ARCES
58678.2130	110.3	ARCES
58696.3201	2.9	ARCES
58707.1337	-57.1	ARCES

Table A.2. Radial velocity measurements of the He I $\lambda 6678$ line of V1362 Cyg.

Date MJD	Radial velocity [km s ⁻¹]	Source
55087.8210	84.9	BeSS echelle
55475.8571	58.4	BeSS H α
56564.8834	80.0	BeSS H α
57219.1265	-85.4	BeSS H α
57985.8713	59.3	BeSS echelle
58314.9210	46.3	BeSS H α
58381.2072	96.6	BeSS H α
58719.8686	88.5	BeSS H α
58723.8628	75.9	BeSS H α
58725.9755	77.3	BeSS echelle
58732.9037	47.2	BeSS H α
58735.8035	1.4	BeSS H α
58737.8701	-23.8	BeSS H α
58738.9377	-30.1	BeSS echelle
58775.8221	83.1	BeSS echelle
58787.7905	53.9	BeSS H α
59069.9488	44.0	BeSS echelle
59092.8965	-95.3	BeSS echelle
59109.8971	60.2	BeSS H α
59135.8555	-35.0	BeSS echelle
59140.8355	-67.8	BeSS echelle
59160.8820	-42.2	BeSS H α
59161.8537	-17.5	BeSS echelle
59174.7977	86.2	BeSS echelle
59358.4160	23.8	ARCES
59364.4184	-39.5	ARCES
59536.1086	-34.6	ARCES
59538.1148	-58.4	ARCES
59540.1212	-71.9	ARCES
59544.0662	-68.3	ARCES
59741.4843	71.9	ARCES
59837.2629	-75.5	ARCES

Table A.3. Radial velocity measurements of the He I $\lambda 6678$ line of V742 Cas.

Date MJD	Radial velocity [km s ⁻¹]	Source
52139.0222	13.9	BeSS H α
52236.8472	-80.4	BeSS H α
52245.8149	-37.3	BeSS H α
52252.8496	32.4	BeSS H α
52255.7934	49.4	BeSS H α
52488.1082	80.0	BeSS H α
52856.1244	-60.7	BeSS H α
54041.8086	15.9	BeSS H α
54371.8752	-38.2	BeSS H α
54763.8919	-34.6	BeSS H α
55103.9794	11.2	BeSS echelle
55458.9127	25.6	BeSS echelle
56186.0120	18.9	BeSS H α
56906.0273	64.2	BeSS echelle
57624.0323	33.7	BeSS echelle
57752.8851	18.4	BeSS echelle
58342.9813	-43.1	BeSS H α
58796.2345	18.0	BeSS echelle
59092.0670	41.3	BeSS echelle
59536.0784	56.2	ARCES
59536.2520	55.7	ARCES
59538.0499	48.5	ARCES
59540.2271	36.9	ARCES
59618.1174	-109.6	ARCES
59624.1090	-80.0	ARCES
59629.0900	-37.3	ARCES
59740.4602	-44.0	ARCES
59824.2356	-4.0	ARCES
59837.4067	-105.5	ARCES
59856.3928	-1.3	ARCES
59865.3794	59.3	ARCES

Table A.4. Radial velocity measurements of the He I $\lambda 6678$ line of HD 44637. Early Measurements obtained from BeSS H α -region spectra might be unreliable, in particular the high positive value.

Date MJD	Radial velocity [km s ⁻¹]	Source
54907.9002	37.75	BeSS H α
56012.8501	84.44	BeSS H α
56394.8729	8.99	BeSS H α
56701.9626	-16.17	BeSS H α
59123.1893	-11.24	BeSS echelle
59940.9157	-36.39	BeSS echelle
59948.9259	-35.03	BeSS echelle
59953.2194	-34.14	ARCES
59957.2038	-39.09	ARCES
59957.9674	-37.29	BeSS echelle
59965.9706	-32.80	BeSS echelle
59966.1661	-31.44	ARCES
59966.9466	-31.90	BeSS echelle
59971.9631	-28.76	BeSS echelle
59974.1632	-27.86	ARCES
59976.9469	-26.96	BeSS echelle
59982.7880	-24.70	BeSS echelle
59987.9495	-24.70	BeSS echelle
60006.9798	-7.64	BeSS echelle
60011.0913	-4.04	UVES
60013.8808	-8.98	BeSS echelle
60018.8889	2.25	BeSS echelle
60020.8628	-0.90	BeSS echelle
60022.8785	2.69	BeSS echelle
60027.8621	4.05	BeSS echelle
60035.0275	17.06	UVES
60036.8701	19.76	BeSS echelle

Fig. A.1. H α line example spectra of the candidate systems. The velocity scale for HR 3195 is different.

Fig. A.2. Blue spectral regions for the higher-confidence candidates for which high-resolution spectra are available, and two synthetic spectra with solar abundances for comparison (computed by Shokry et al. 2018, for $v \sin i = 20 \text{ km s}^{-1}$; see there for details). Spectra are sorted bottom to top in approximate order of increasing effective temperature, as identified in the middle panel. The RV-variable spectra have been shifted to line up photospheric signatures; as a consequence interstellar and telluric features do not match in wavelength.

Fig. A.3. Like Fig. A.2, but for red spectral regions. Strong diffuse interstellar bands are marked DIB.

Fig. A.4. Equivalent to Figs. A.2 and A.3, but for the unconfirmed candidates HR 8107 (ARCES) and HR 4930 (FEROS). No such spectra are available for V505 Mon and V658 Car.

Appendix B: Interferometric data

This section gives tables and example plots for the interferometric observations and their analysis.

variability of the narrow lines. But the number of spectra with sufficient quality is not high enough for a definite conclusion.

Appendix C: Other Be stars with composite spectra

During the inspection of the BeSS database, several objects stood out as being recognized as single, classical Be stars in the database, but showing in fact composite spectra. For some of them, this information could be found in the literature, but not all. Those for which the composite nature seems unpublished are listed below.

Appendix C.1: Be stars with probable late-type companions

Since the spectra of the following objects are composite, this indicates that the late type spectrum must be of giant-type, as otherwise it would not have been detectable against the B star spectrum, so that they must be low contrast binaries in any case. These might be stars in the process of being stripped, as the ones mentioned in Sect. 4.2

12 Aur (HD 33988) is a binary, with at least two sets of absorption lines. In spite of being known as a Be star for nearly a century (Merrill & Burwell, 1933), the literature on this object is rather sparse, which might be due to the proximity of Capella, less than half a degree away. Whether both spectra are countermoving or the B star spectrum is moving at all is difficult to assess at the data quality. Certainly one spectrum is rather narrow and much later than B2, of spectral type F, and moves with $K = 70 \text{ km s}^{-1}$ and a period of 10.7959 d on a circular orbit. The other spectrum is near-stationary and that of an early B-type star. The observed variations of the Balmer emission lines makes it more likely to be an interacting system with ongoing mass transfer, but this is certainly not a final verdict and further observations would be necessary for any firm judgment.

V415 Aur (HD 33461): The second spectrum is of type F. He I $\lambda 6678$, supposedly from the B-type companion, might show signs of RV variability. There is only one echelle spectrum, so no period analysis can be undertaken, but the more than a dozen H α -spectra show variability typical for an interacting binary.

BD+62 271 (MWC 14): A late-type Be-star spectrum, superimposed with a K-type spectrum. The narrow-lined K component is RV variable with several tens of km s^{-1} amplitude.

HD 174512: There is H α emission, but the spectrum is a clear composite of an early A-type star and a much later narrow-lined component. The BeSS database also includes one FEROS spectrum, where the strong hydrogen lines belonging to the A-type star can be well seen in the Balmer and Paschen sequence.

HD 55806 shows a composite spectrum of a mid to late Be type star with Be-typical emission line profiles plus a G-type absorption spectrum. There is one FEROS spectrum in BeSS that confirms the composite nature.

Appendix C.2: Be stars with probable early-type companions

HD 12856: The spectrum is reminiscent of HR 4930 (see Sect. 3.8.2) and shows broad-lined spectrum of early B-type, superimposed with an unresolved line spectrum of a mid-type B star. There is some indication for low-amplitude RV

Table B.1. Log of interferometric observations

Target	Instrument	Band/Resolution	MJD _{mean}	UT date	Calibrator
LB-1	VLT/GRAVITY	<i>K</i> -low	59604.090	2022 Jan 25	TYC 1877-265-1
V742 Cas	CHARA/MIRC-X	<i>H</i>	59732.502	2022 Jun 2	HD 240440
V742 Cas	CHARA/MIRC-X	<i>H</i>	59763.495	2022 Jul 3	HD 240440
V742 Cas	CHARA/MIRC-X	<i>H</i>	59777.408	2022 Jul 17	HD 240440
V742 Cas	CHARA/MIRC-X	<i>H</i>	59818.400	2022 Aug 27	HD 240440
V742 Cas	CHARA/MIRC-X	<i>H</i>	59855.222	2022 Oct 3	HD 240440
V742 Cas	CHARA/MIRC-X	<i>H</i>	59878.245	2022 Oct 26	HD 8992
V742 Cas	CHARA/MYSTIC	<i>K</i>	59732.502	2022 Jun 2	HD 240440
V742 Cas	CHARA/MYSTIC	<i>K</i>	59763.493	2022 Jul 3	HD 240440
V742 Cas	CHARA/MYSTIC	<i>K</i>	59777.408	2022 Jul 17	HD 240440
V742 Cas	CHARA/MYSTIC	<i>K</i>	59818.404	2022 Aug 27	HD 240440
V742 Cas	CHARA/MYSTIC	<i>K</i>	59855.222	2022 Oct 3	HD 240440
V742 Cas	CHARA/MYSTIC	<i>K</i>	59878.245	2022 Oct 26	HD 8992
V447 Sct	CHARA/MIRC-X	<i>H</i>	59763.252	2022 Jul 3	HD 155662
V447 Sct	CHARA/MIRC-X	<i>H</i>	59777.250	2022 Jul 17	HD 166161
V447 Sct	CHARA/MYSTIC	<i>K</i>	59763.251	2022 Jul 3	HD 155662
V447 Sct	CHARA/MYSTIC	<i>K</i>	59777.250	2022 Jul 17	HD 166161
V1362 Cyg	CHARA/MIRC-X	<i>H</i>	59763.438	2022 Jul 3	SAO 68453
HR 2309	VLT/GRAVITY	<i>K</i> -high	59928.199	2022 Dec 15	HD 44760
HD 44637	VLT/GRAVITY	<i>K</i> -high	59928.279	2022 Dec 15	HD 44414
V1371 Tau	VLT/GRAVITY	<i>K</i> -high	59964.068	2023 Jan 20	HD 245813
HR 2309	VLT/GRAVITY	<i>K</i> -high	59972.055	2023 Jan 28	HD 44760
HR 3195	VLT/GRAVITY	<i>K</i> -high	59989.215	2023 Feb 14	HD 67509
HD 44637	VLT/GRAVITY	<i>K</i> -high	59997.105	2023 Feb 22	HD 44414

Table B.2. Interferometric calibrators and their uniform disk (UD) angular diameters

Calibrator	UD diam. (<i>H</i>) [mas]	UD diam. (<i>K</i>) [mas]
TYC 1877-265-1	0.037 ± 0.001	0.037 ± 0.001
HD 240440	0.371 ± 0.008	0.373 ± 0.008
HD 8992	0.353 ± 0.010	0.354 ± 0.010
HD 155662	0.431 ± 0.012	0.433 ± 0.012
HD 166161	0.382 ± 0.010	0.384 ± 0.010
SAO 68453	0.242 ± 0.005	0.243 ± 0.005
HD 44760	0.271 ± 0.007	0.272 ± 0.007
HD 44414	0.185 ± 0.005	0.186 ± 0.005
HD 245813	0.201 ± 0.005	0.202 ± 0.005
HD 67509	0.368 ± 0.010	0.370 ± 0.010

Table B.3. Relative astrometric positions and flux ratios of the V742 Cas binary determined from the squared visibilities and closure phases.

MJD _{mean}	ρ [mas]	PA [°]	Δ RA [mas]	Δ DEC [mas]	σ - <i>a</i> [mas]	σ - <i>b</i> [mas]	σ -PA [°]	<i>f</i> [% primary]	Band
59732.502	0.5974	279.544	-0.5891	0.0991	0.0035	0.0032	200.85	49.9 ^{+0.6} _{-0.7}	<i>H</i>
59763.495	0.5153	87.936	0.5150	0.0186	0.0028	0.0027	76.79	48.3 ^{+0.3} _{-0.4}	<i>H</i>
59777.408	0.5203	320.519	-0.3308	0.4016	0.0029	0.0028	197.04	45.0 ^{+0.6} _{-0.5}	<i>H</i>
59818.400	0.5619	94.429	0.5602	-0.0434	0.0046	0.0032	115.91	40.8 ^{+0.3} _{-0.4}	<i>H</i>
59855.222	0.3441	190.692	-0.0638	-0.3381	0.0046	0.0026	85.16	38.2 ^{+1.9} _{-2.1}	<i>H</i>
59878.245	0.4160	67.428	0.3841	0.1597	0.0054	0.0035	88.46	38.4 ^{+1.2} _{-1.1}	<i>H</i>
59732.502	0.6164	280.909	-0.6053	0.1167	0.0050	0.0042	144.68	55.9 ^{+0.7} _{-0.8}	<i>K</i>
59763.493	0.5159	88.496	0.5157	0.0135	0.0035	0.0031	201.81	58.3 ^{+0.8} _{-0.8}	<i>K</i>
59777.408	0.5187	319.372	-0.3377	0.3937	0.0040	0.0030	152.57	54.6 ^{+1.3} _{-1.4}	<i>K</i>
59818.403	0.5577	94.250	0.5562	-0.0413	0.0036	0.0031	84.47	51.9 ^{+0.7} _{-0.7}	<i>K</i>
59855.222	0.3977	195.245	-0.1046	-0.3837	0.0116	0.0086	87.36	32.3 ^{+3.0} _{-3.4}	<i>K</i>
59878.245	0.4261	74.469	0.4105	0.1141	0.0125	0.0105	74.47	37.1 ^{+3.7} _{-3.9}	<i>K</i>

Notes. ρ is the angular separation between the components, PA is the position angle (from North to East), Δ RA and Δ DEC are the companion coordinates relative to the primary, σ -*a* and σ -*b* are the major and minor axes of the error ellipse, respectively, σ -PA is the position angle of the error ellipse (from North to East), and *f* is the secondary-to-primary flux fraction. The two points taken latest have separations below the nominal resolution, which results in systematically lower *f* for both instruments. Both components are unresolved and their corresponding diameters were fixed to small values for the binary fit.

Fig. B.1. PMOIRED analysis of the GRAVITY observation of HD 44637 from 2022 Dec 15. Top left: Binned closure phases (T3PHI) and visibilities ($|V|$) vs. the spatial frequency, used to determine the relative position and flux ratio of the two binary components. Overplotted is the best-fit binary model (solid lines), with the corresponding residuals in units of σ in the bottom panels. Top right: Binary image on sky with primary being the brighter component. Bottom left: Full spectral resolution observables including the normalized flux (NFLUX) and differential phase (DPHI) vs. the wavelength across Br γ with the best-fit model overplotted in red. Bottom right: Flux contributions from both components across Br γ . The brighter primary is the Be star showing line emission in Br γ , while the secondary stripped component shows no discernible line profile in Br γ .

Fig. B.2. PMOIRED analysis of MIRC-X observation of V742 Cas from 2022 Aug 27. Closure phases (T3PHI) and squared visibilities (V2) vs. spatial frequency are overplotted with the best-fit binary model (solid), with the bottom panels showing the corresponding residuals in units of σ .